

Studies in Zirconium Oxide Sols. Part II. Hydration of Micelles in Zirconium Oxide Sols

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Hydration of the micelles in the case of zirconium oxide sol has been studied by considering the distribution of an electrolyte (NH_4Cl) as a reference substance across a semipermeable membrane. Neglecting the membrane equilibrium effect, the value of hydration comes out to be 62 moles of water per mole of zirconium oxide. This value is in agreement with that obtained by viscosity method. The charge on the micelles has been found to be 0.4 m.e. of NO_3^- per g. of zirconium oxide.

Properties of metallic oxide sols are known to be governed by the charge as well as the solvation of the micelles. Coagulation of a sol by a mixture of electrolytes may partly be explained by the change in hydration of the micelles in presence of foreign substances. Very few attempts have been made to measure the extent of hydration quantitatively. In the present investigation, hydration of micelles has been measured by studying the distribution of ammonium chloride across a semipermeable membrane in presence of colloidal zirconium oxide. Alternatively, viscosity measurements may also be employed to measure the extent of hydration.

EXPERIMENTAL

Methods of preparation and analysis of zirconium oxide sols have been reported earlier (*this issue*, p. 288). To determine NH_4^+ ion, an aliquot portion of the sol was coagulated with sodium sulphate, filtered, and washed till free of ammonium ion. An excess of a standard solution of NaOH was added to the filtrate and washings. The solution was then boiled till free of ammonia, cooled, an excess of a standard HCl solution added, and the unused acid was titrated against NaOH (Vogel, "A Text-Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 1955, p. 505).

A partially dialysed sol was mixed with ammonium chloride (far below its c.v.) and was kept in collodion bags, suspended in water. After equilibrium, the sol inside and the liquid outside the bag were analysed. ZrO_2 was found to be absent outside the bag. Some of the results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

ZrO ₂ conc. (I—E)*.	Diff. in NO ₃ ⁻ (I—E).	Conc. of NO ₃ ⁻ (m. e. per g. of colloid).		Conc. of ammonium ion (m.e./litre).			S.H.V.
		NO ₃ ⁻ (I—E) ZrO ₂ (I—E)	I.	E.	D.		
23.20 g./litre	8.0 m.e./litre	0.34	8.88	11.28	0.1090	52.6	
22.60	8.0	0.35	9.20	11.60	0.1092	52.5	
22.60	8.0	0.35	8.96	11.36	0.1070	53.6	
22.40	12.0	0.54	9.20	11.60	0.1083	52.9	
23.20	12.0	0.52	9.12	11.68	0.1067	53.7	
22.60	8.0	0.35	9.20	11.60	0.1092	52.5	
		Mean 0.41			0.1082	52.9	

*Concentration of ZrO_2 outside the membrane (E) is nil.

DISCUSSION

The concentration of ammonium ion outside the membrane appears from Table I to be greater than that inside the bag, reverse being the case with NO_3^- ions. The NO_3^- ions

are gegenions and are found both in the fixed and the free conditions. From the concentrations of NO_3^- ions inside and outside the bag, fixed NO_3^- ion/g. of zirconium oxide may be calculated; it comes out to be 0.4 m.e. of nitrate ion per g. of ZrO_2 .

The unequal distribution of NH_4^+ ion across a semipermeable membrane may be due to (a) hydration of the micelles or (b) the membrane equilibrium effect. Either may be calculated if one is known. It was not found possible to measure either of these effects independently. If the concentration of the diffusible ion is much greater than that of the non-diffusible ion (only a fraction of which will be active towards membrane equilibrium), the membrane equilibrium effect may, however, be considered of lesser importance and the unequal distribution of NH_4^+ ion across the membrane may be attributed to the hydration effect. In that case, the apparent density (D) and specific hydrodynamic volume (S.H.V.) may be calculated as shown before (Trivedi and Patani, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1954, 40A, 119). Taking the average value of S.H.V. as 53 (Table I) and the density of zirconium oxide as 5.73 g./c.c. ("Chemical Engineer's Hand Book," 1941, p. 367), there will be 52 g. of non-solvent water to 5.73 g. of zirconium oxide. Thus, there are $(52/18) \times (1000/5.73) = 504.1$ of mM water per g. of zirconium oxide. The molecular weight of zirconium oxide (ZrO_2) is 123.22. Therefore there are $(504.1/1000) \times 123.22 = 62$ (approx.) moles of water per mole of zirconium oxide. The actual value of hydration will be slightly less than this value if the Donnan membrane equilibrium effect is taken in consideration.

Another method of evaluating the hydration of the micelles is to study the variation in specific viscosity of the sol on dilution. The method has been discussed in detail previously (Trivedi *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 685). The hydration values, calculated in this way, were plotted against concentration. The apparent hydration values increase with increase in concentration so that the real value of hydration can be obtained by plotting the hydration values at lower concentrations and extrapolating the curve to zero concentration. The rapid increase in viscosity and apparent values of hydration are due to the non-Newtonian behaviour of the sol at a finite concentration. The values of hydration obtained by extrapolating the curve to zero concentration is found to be 55 moles of water per mole of zirconium oxide (data not given). Thus hydration values obtained by both the methods are of the same order. This was found also to be the case with aluminium oxide sols (Trivedi *et al.*, *loc. cit.*).

To understand the contribution of hydration towards the stability of colloidal systems, it would be necessary to know not only the extent of hydration but also the nature of hydration. There are three types of bound water in colloidal systems (Jirgensons and Straumanis, "Colloidal Chemistry", 1954, p. 326):

- (1) Tightly bound water (hydrogen bonds).
- (2) Loosely adsorbed water by dipole attraction and cohesion.
- (3) Immobilised water.

The last type exists principally in gels. The first type alone may have a definite value, whereas the second as well as the third will show wide variations. To determine the influence of hydration on stability, it will be necessary to determine the extent of each type of hydration. Only then it will be possible to comprehend the effect of solvation on the stability of colloidal systems.

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